

TALAB VA TAKLIF NAZARIYASI VA UNI BOZOR MUVONATIGA TA'SIRI

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Annotatsiya. Makro va mikroiqtisodiyotda talab, taklif hamda bozor muvozanati tushunchalari asosiy kriteriyalar hisoblanadi. Mazkur maqolada aytib o'tilgan yo'nalishlarning mohiyati, bir-biriga bog'liqligi muhokama etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Talab, taklif, bozor muvozanati, savdo, daromad, metod.

THEORY OF SUPPLY AND DEMAND AND ITS MARKET RELATIONSHIP EFFECT

Abstract. In macro and microeconomics, the concepts of demand, supply and market balance are the main criteria. This article discusses the essence and interdependence of the directions mentioned.

Key words: Demand, supply, market equilibrium, trade, income, method.

ТЕОРИЯ СПРОСА И ПРЕДЛОЖЕНИЯ И ЕГО РЫНОЧНЫЕ ОТНОШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТ

Аннотация. В макро- и микроэкономике основными критериями являются понятия спроса, предложения и рыночного баланса. В данной статье рассматривается сущность и взаимозависимость упомянутых направлений.

Ключевые слова: Спрос, предложение, рыночное равновесие, торговля, доход, метод.

KIRISH

Mamlakatimizda mustaqillik yillarida olib borilgan to'g'ri va izchil iqtisodiy siyosat orqali ahamiyatli ijobiy natijalar qo'lga kiritildi. Jumladan, O'zbekistonda talab va taklifning o'zaro mutanosibligi negizida milliy xo'jaligimiz iqtisodiy jihatdan mustahkamlanib, ma'muriy-buyruqbozlik tizimdan meros bo'lib qolgan bir tomonlamalik va inqiroz holatidan chiqarildi; iqtisodiyotning barqaror o'sishi ta'minlandi, makroiqtisodiy va moliyaviy barqarorlik mustahkamlandi, iqtisodiyot va uning ayrim sohalaridagi mutanosiblik kuchaydi; bozor mexanizmining tarkibiy qismlari qaror topdi va uning infratuzilmalari vujudga keltirilib, rivojlantirildi.

TADQIQOT METODOLOGIYASI VA EMPIRIK TAHLIL

Ehtiyoj kishilarning hayotiy vositalariga bo'lgan zaruriyatini ifodalovchi ilmiy kategoriya sifatida taraqqiyotning hamma bosqichlari uchun umumiy va doimiydir.

Uning bozor iqtisodiyoti sharoitidagi tarixiy ko'rinishi talab tushunchasidir.

Talab ehtiyojdan farq qilib, mustaqil iqtisodiy kategoriya (ilmiy tushuncha) sifatida amal qiladi.

Ehtiyojning faqat pul bilan ta'minlangan qismi talabga aylanadi. Demak, talab – bu pul bilan ta'minlangan ehtiyojdir. Ehtiyoj zarur miqdordagi pul bilan ta'minlanmasa, u «xohish», «istak» bo'lib qolaveradi. Talabning bir qator muqobil variantlari mavjud bo'ladi, chunki narx o'zgarishi bilan tovarning sotibolinadigan miqdori ham o'zgaradi. Shu bog'liqlikdan kelib chiqib, talabga quyidagicha ta'rif berish mumkin: ma'lum vaqt oralig'ida, narxlarning mavjud darajasida

iste'molchilarning tovar va xizmatlar ma'lum turlarini sotib olishga qodir bo'lgan ehtiyoji talab deyiladi.

Talablar turlicha bo'lib, odatda bir xil tovar yoki xizmatlarga bo'lgan talabning ikki turi farq qilinadi: yakka talab va bozor talabi. Har bir iste'molchining, ya'ni alohida shaxs, oila, korxonalar, firmaning tovarning shu turiga bo'lgan talabi yakka talab deyiladi. Bir qancha (ko'pchilik) iste'molchilarning shu turdagi tovar yoki xizmatga bo'lgan talablari yig'indisi bozor talabi deyiladi.

Narx va sotib olinadigan tovarlar miqdori o'rtasidagi bo'ladigan bog'liqlikni quyidagi 1-jadval ma'lumotlari asosida qarab chiqamiz.

Narx va sotib olinadigan tovar miqdori o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik.

1 - jadval

Bir kg un narxi (so'm)	1 oy davomida unga bo'lgan yakka talab miqdori (kg)	1 oy davomida unga bo'lgan bozor talabi miqdori (tn)
350	10	1,0
300	20	2,0
250	30	3,0
200	50	5,0
150	60	6,0

Jadval ma'lumotlari tovar narxining pasayishi sotib olinadigan tovar miqdorining o'sishiga va aksincha, narxning o'sishi talab miqdorining kamayishiga olib kelishini ko'rsatadi. Mahsulot narxi va sotib olinadigan tovar miqdori o'zgarishi o'rtasida bo'ladigan teskari yoki qarama-qarshi bog'liqlik talab qonuni deyiladi.

Tovar narxi va uning xarid qilinadigan miqdori (talabning) o'rtasidagi teskari bog'liqlikni oddiy ikki o'lchamli grafikda ham tasvirlash mumkin: yotiqchiziq talab miqdorini, tik chiziq narxni ko'rsatadi (1-chizma).

1-chizma. Talab egri chizig'i

Ma'lum vaqt oralig'idagi narxlarning muayyan darajasida ishlab chiqaruvchi yoki sotuvchilar tomonidan ma'lum turdagi tovar va xizmatlarning bozorga chiqarilgan miqdori taklif deyiladi. Narx o'zgarishi bilan sotishga chiqariladigan mahsulot miqdori ham o'zgarishi sababli talab kabi taklifning ham bir qator muqobil variantlari mavjud bo'ladi.

Taklif narxlarning turli darajasida qancha miqdordagi mahsulotning sotishga chiqarilishini ko'rsatadi.

Narxning oshishi bilan shunga mos ravishda sotishga chiqariladigan tovarlar taklifi miqdori ham ortadi, narxning tushishi bilan taklif hajmi qisqaradi. Narxning o'zgarishi bilan taklif etilayotgan tovar miqdorining to'g'ri bog'liqlikdagi o'zgarishi taklif qonuni deyiladi.

Narx va taklif miqdori o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik.

2-jadval

1 kg un narxi (so'm)	1 oy davomida unning yakka taklifi miqdori (kg)	1 oy davomida unning bozor taklifi miqdori (tn)
350	60	6,0
300	50	5,0
250	30	3,0
200	20	2,0
150	10	1,0

Iste'molchi uchun narxning oshishi to'siq rolini o'ynasa, ishlab chiqaruvchi uchun rag'batlantirish vazifasini bajaradi.

Biz yuqorida turli omillar ta'sirida talab va taklif miqdorining o'zgarib turishini ko'rdik.

Lekin talab bilan taklif miqdorlari bir-birlari bilan doimo ma'lum nisbatda bo'ladi, bu nisbatlar o'zgarib turadi. Ba'zantalab miqdori taklif miqdoridan oshib ketib, narx ko'tirilsa, ayrim paytda taklif miqdori talab miqdoridan oshib ketib, narx pasayib qoladi. Talabmiqdori bilan taklif miqdori o'rtasidagi nisbat bir-biriga teng bo'lgan holat bozor muvozanati deyiladi.

XULOSA VA MUNOZARA

Bozor muvozanati vujudga kelgan holda shakllangan narx bozor narxi deyiladi. Ba'zan uni muvozanatlashgan narx ham debyurtiladi. Bozor muvozanati va muvozanatli narx har doim mavjud bo'lib turmaydi, ularga ta'sir qiluvchi ko'plab omillar muvozanatlikning buzilishiga sabab bo'ladi.

Ammo iqtisodiyotda ushbu muvozanatga doimo intilish mavjud bo'ladi.

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